

SMART GRID ELLEVIO- DEMO STOCKHOLM

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes Ellevio's, a Swedish DSO, deliverables within the Horizon 2020 EU financed project; Integrid- demo Stockholm. Ellevio has demo sites located in Stockholm (Ekerö, Kyrkviken and Stockholm Royal Seaport, SRS), including primary and secondary substations, with the main goal to increase the reliability in the grid by using new technology and "time of use tariffs" for residential customers.

The main parts under study at the demo sites are fault localization, predictive maintenance, load forecasting and potential for demand response, DR. Preliminary results has shown that fault indicators at Ekerö could make a positive business case after only a few faults and by using information from the protective relays a good estimate of the fault location can be achieved. Moreover, in Stockholm Royal Seaport studies has shown benefits with a higher level of monitoring on the secondary substations to verify that the power quality is within acceptable limit and the ability to analyse outages in retrospect. In Kyrkviken a centralized protection and control system are installed and results on voltage regulation function are presented and tests on predictive maintenance will be carried out.

INTRODUCTION

Ellevio is one of the largest DSO in Sweden with nearly one million customers. Together with EDP and Electro Ljubljana, Ellevio make up the DSOs in the Integrid project with the vision to bridge the gap between citizens and technology. In addition to the DSO, the consortium consists of Universities, research institutes and solution providers. [1]

The Stockholm demo consists of four different demo-areas presented in Figure 1, and including KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Aktiva Huset, LocalLife and Ellevio with the aim to increase the consumer engagement through new technologies increasing the reliability of the electric grid. By Ellevio this is done through predictive maintenance, fault localization and load forecasting in demo area 1, 3 and 4. Moreover, on the consumer side, Aktiva Huset, and LocalLife, are using technologies and methods such as in-home displays and local social network in demo area 1 and 2.

Figure 1. Location of the Demo sites in Stockholm.

Within the Integrid project Ellevio is sharing results from three smart grid demo sites: Ekerö, Kyrkviken and Stockholm Royal Seaport (SRS).

At Ekerö, fault indicators is tested to reduce outage time and to reduce the number of customers affected. The indicators together with the communication system and the integration into the dispatch center (DC) have been successfully deployed and the indicators have detected, as expected, a number of faults. The next step is to collect more information about the actual faults and to optimize the total process from outage to the energizing of the network including the field repair organization and the dispatch center personnel.

At Lidingö, a pilot is ongoing with the main goal to evaluate the centralized protection and control system architecture (CPC). The system is implemented to achieve simplification for managing the protection relays and to enable for third party functionalities. The system has a voltage regulation function and the potential to introduce predictive maintenance and load forecasting. Initial studies have been done on how to implement predictive maintenance by using asset health indexes. The studies will be further developed by Ellevio and by the global solution provider SAP, using data processing.

SRS is a newly built district in the central part of Stockholm with the aim to considerably reduce environmental impact of energy consumption [2]. Ellevio has tested different solutions on how to build the future grid by introducing low loss transformers, wireless communication, load forecasting and increased level of monitoring. Preliminary studies has shown a vast potential in the secondary substations with increased number of measured parameters and increased resolution on the data when it comes to studies on power quality and post-

mortem outage analysis. Moreover, predictive maintenance is dependent on that more data is collected. This is beneficial for the DSO and will be an advantage in the near future due to the expected increased penetration of electric vehicles (EV), and solar panels, PV. Moreover, by engaging the consumers with incentivized “time of use tariffs” and building models for load forecasting and DR, the capacity in the network can be optimized

ELLEVIO DEMO SITES

In this chapter Ellevio’s demonstration sites’ smart grid technology, such as sensors and wireless communication, the predictive maintenance and fault localization, are described in more detail.

A short description of the properties, main functions and objectives at the different sites are presented in table 1.

Table 1. Ellevios Infrastructure

Infrastructure Swedish Demo		
Demo site	Properties and main functions	Objectives
Ekerö	Fault indicators using GSM/SMS technology connected to DMS/SCADA for locating faulty sections in the MV grid. Two sections with a total of 1024 LV (5-15 kW) clients. Fast reenergized clients on non-affected sections.	Fault location, isolation and restoration
Kyrkviken	Primary substation 70/10 kV, 12 MV clients and 22000 LV clients. Retrofitted with a centralized protection and control system. Voltage regulation capabilities.	Predictive maintenance. Voltage regulation. Load forecasting.
Stockholm Royal Seaport	Four secondary substations, whereof three new and one retrofit, 2x800 kVA, 1x800 kVA, 1x800 kVA, 4x1000 kVA. 200-300 LV clients (5-15 kW/client) per station. The substations has different levels of control, monitoring and measurements such as: Control, Fault Detection/Protection, Power Quality, Measurement and Analysis, Automatic Switching, Remote Asset Management. Within Ellevios infrastructure not included in Ellevios deliverables are Residential DRSM system, EV charging stations and PV installations. Wireless communication 3G/4G.	Monitoring Predictive maintenance Load forecasting
Duration		
In operation as of February 2017 no plans of removal of the equipment		
Medium	Area	Voltage levels [kV]
Electricity	Urban/rural	70/20/10/0.4

Ekerö

The purpose with the demo in Ekerö is to reduce outage time and to reduce the number of customers affected during a fault by using fault indicators together with remote disconnectors.

The grid at Ekerö can be seen as a rural grid with a mixture between underground cable and overhead line. This makes a test pilot for fault detectors perfect because of the usual long fault localization time, which leads to long interruption times and high cost for field personnel and customer minutes lost effecting the income frame. The indicators are placed on the poles for overhead lines and in the secondary substations for underground cables, see Figure 2.

The placement of the detectors depend on network structure, number of customers effected, historical faults and experience of the field and DC personnel. A study within the Integrid project has been done on the fault localization and isolation process comparing placement

against investments costs and affected customers [3]. Within the pilot, a total number of 12 indicators have been installed, eight on overhead lines and four on underground cables.

Figure 2. Fault detectors at Ekerö a) overhead line, b) and c) underground cable.

The Fault indicators can detect line to line and line to ground faults. Communication is done through GSM to a GSM link router, which in turn communicate with the supervisory control and data acquisition (SCADA) system. The detectors are equipped with a lithium battery for power supply with eight years of estimated operation. The overhead line detectors uses the electric and magnetic field to detect a fault whereas the detectors for underground cable uses current sensors.

The work in the Integrid project is to integrate the detectors together with remote disconnectors into advanced distribution management system (ADMS) and to identify how much this kind of equipment can reduce SAIDI, CAIDI and energy not supplied, resulting in a higher income frame that can finance the new smart system with good profitability.

Moreover, by introducing a historical database of the faults occurring and which equipment usually fails the fault location process might be further reduced and the need of personnel with previous knowledge of the area will be of less importance.

So far the integration into the ADMS has been done and work on an historical database have started but the study depends on that real faults occur and that the tools in ADMS are used by the personnel in the DC. The next step is to use the indicators together with information from the protection relays in the primary substations to be able to locate the fault position and using remote disconnectors to isolate sections of the grid keeping the number of effected customers down to a minimum. Simulations in the ADMS test environment has been carried out to study the fault location, isolation and supply restoration (FLISR) system and it shows very good possibilities to restore the power to the customers and to locate the faults. Figure 3 presents the structure of the two sections in Ekerö in the ADMS test environment.

Figure 3. Fault indicators at one of the sites at Ekerö, a) Snapshot from the ADMS system, b) Grid structure and placement of fault indicators.

Kyrkviken

Kyrkviken primary substation is located on Lidingö in Stockholm. The station has two parallel 20 MVA, 70/10 kV transformers and the customers are mainly residential and a few larger plants and factories. In 2014 the station was retrofitted with a CPC system which runs in shadow mode to the old protection system. The CPC system use one central CPU for protection and control instead of using distributed intelligent electronic devices (IEDs) in each bay. By replacing the IEDs by I/O modules in each bay, the life expectancy is believed to increase. Moreover less functionality in each bay will make the system more perspicuous. Each module is connected to the central CPU through optical fibre. The CPU is built upon a flexible platform enabling implementations of new functions such as predictive maintenance and load forecasting. Figure 4 present the conceptual architecture of the CPC-system and shows the optical fibre from each I/O module connected to the CPU.

Figure 4. The centralized relay and control system at Kyrkviken, a) One of the centralized control unit b) An overview of the control system in Kyrkviken.

Because of the type of customers connected to the station, the load profile varies considerable during the course of the day. To compensate for this tap-changers on the transformers are regulated several times a day. The tap-changers are controlled by the CPC-system and has 19 taps each that can regulate the voltage by 1.67 %.

The main area to study within the Integrid project in Kyrkviken is voltage regulation, predictive maintenance and load forecast. A study of the voltage regulation is presented in [4]. During the study, the maximum deviation

from the set voltage was only 1.8 %, see Figure 5.

Figure 5. Voltage data from 1/3 to 10/3 2017. The time resolution is five minutes. The lines indicate the set voltage and the lower and upper voltage limits.

Moreover, studies of fault response, signal correlation and overall protection functionality of the CPC system has been investigated.

To improve reliability index and to avoid fatal errors and reduce maintenance cost by for example unnecessary local maintenance in Kyrkviken, predictive maintenance will be tested. In Kyrkviken the predictive maintenance will mainly focus on the oil-isolated transformers using parameters such as load and ambient temperature. The algorithms are to be developed by SAP as a part of the Integrid project. SAP, the third party solution provider, will use methods like Duval Triangle, Duval Pentagon, IEC basic gas ratios, Chendong DP for health indication and probability of failure.

Stockholm Royal Seaport

SRS is located in the central parts of Stockholm with a typical urban structure with double cable system. The typical customer in the area is residential, there are also PV-installations and EV-charging stations connected to the secondary substations. The focus has been to increase reliability and operation of the medium voltage distribution grid by collecting more data implement a higher level of monitoring. Four secondary substations are included in the SRS demo area 3, where the main goals is to increase the reliability of the network.

An in-depth description of the secondary substations can be found in [5, 6]. In this paper, the focus will be on the measurements, load forecasting and implementation of predictive maintenance.

The number of parameters measured or calculated varies between the stations, and the values are updated every 15 minutes with min, max and average RMS values for each parameter.

The work done so far studying the measurements from the station has indicated a good quality of the measurements. From a reliability perspective, to have access to all the measurements has shown to be very helpful when verifying that the power quality was within the established limits and recommendations. The voltage unbalance and the voltage harmonics were studied during several months and was shown to be well below the limits. In addition,

current harmonics were studied and the results indicated possible negative effects on the stations during full load. However, due to a strong grid and stations not near full load the current harmonics has less influence. The harmonic currents could also be more of an issue in the future due to increased penetration of PVs and EV-chargers in the grid.

The predictive maintenance at this stage will mainly focus on the transformers in the stations. The transformers are of dry type and in two of the stations; the winding temperature on each phase is measured together with the ambient temperature in the station. Within the project, SAP will try to develop a tool adapted for dry transformers to implement predictive maintenance in the stations. For the dry transformers SAP will explore the potential of using load and ambient temperature as described in actual technical literature and recommendations by IEEE. SAP will use the demo environment for additional analysis, e.g. to find patterns that will also help to predict asset health (e.g. comparison of the different phases of the transformer in relation to ambient temperature and load). Preliminary theoretical studies shows a clear connection between load levels, ambient temperature and deterioration rate of the transformers which highlight advantages of increased monitoring and measured parameters. Moreover, harmonics could be a factor to consider due to increasing penetration of EV and PV. Within the cooperation with SAP, Ellevio will also look for the potential to include cable joints and circuit breakers in the predictive maintenance system.

As described earlier the demand response could have a big impact on how the infrastructure are designed in the future. One important part of the demand response is to have a good knowledge on how the load will change in short and long terms by using load forecasting tools. In Figure 6, a snap-shot from the load forecast tool is presented showing aggregated values from 154 apartments. The forecast (red) is compared with the actual load (blue) in kWh in the top figure and the price signal is presented below.

Figure 6. Snap-shot of the forecasting tool during 24h. The top figure present the load forecast (red) compared to the actual load (blue) in kWh. The lower figure presents the price signal.

During the spring 2018 the first unplanned outage occur in one of the stations. The outage lasted for almost two hours in the afternoon and the reason was a damaged medium

voltage cable during excavation work. Three of the affected secondary substations have monitoring systems installed, which allows for further analysis [6]. In Figure 7 one can see that the load directly after the outage, blue line, is higher for about one hour compared to the day before, orange line.

Figure 7. Unplanned outage and returning load.

HISTORICAL DATA

Within all the demo sites, the importance of having historical data is vital to predict the future challenge. A lot of data is already collected and to make use of the data it needs to be interpreted and connected to other functions within the operation of the grid. As a side project a historical database for power failures caused by different types of cable faults has been developed. The database contains 37 different categories with varying information e.g. start and end time, broken part, cable type and geographical area. The input of data was partly done manually, and partly done automatically through two other databases providing more data. Results from the study is presented in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Fault frequency per km cable for different cables in Stockholm region.

When the historical database was completed, a series of problems was solved using the database in order to test the depth of the database and investigate in which way it is proper to use. The solutions showed that the database is able to e.g. compare different cable types in different aspects, search relationships between number of breakdowns and specific joints and differences between geographical areas. It is possible to successfully, create a historical database that can be used to find problems within the power grid. The biggest challenges lies with the choice

of categories and knowledge about the information that the database holds in order to make the right assumptions in the analysis. Figure 8 presents result from the database on fault frequency for different cables in Stockholm.

CONCLUSIONS

- Fault indicators and remote disconnectors on Ekerö has successfully been implemented in ADMS for a faster localization and isolation process. So far there has not been enough faults during 2017 and 2018 at the site to carry out statistical analyse on the proposed reduced outage time.
- A study within the Demo site at Ekerö has shown that by having access to the protection relays information, distance to fault, the amount of fault indicators could be reduced to major branches in the MV-grid. It also showed to be the most affordable solution keeping high accuracy on fault location when considering total costs of equipment and installation.
- Voltage regulation function in the CPC-system shows good performance except for minor indications of the regulation time being undesirably long. This could however be due a consequence of the resolution of the data, which is in five minutes while set regulation time is about two minutes. Few noticeable deviations result in a very stable grid voltage.
- Preliminary studies of the parameters collected in SRS shows that there could be much to gain by monitoring temperature and load of the dry transformer. Moreover current harmonics has been identified as a possible problem with increased load on the stations and a higher penetration of EVs and PVs. Further studies are needed to understand the impact of current harmonics in the future smart grid.
- One fault has occurred in SRS and this pinpoint the problems which can occur with returning load. It also emphasizes the possibilities for deeper analysis as a result of increased monitoring and data collection.
- Load forecasting have been implemented in SRS, presenting aggregated value from 154 apartments. The results look promising, but the commercial potential for aggregated load has not been tested. More work is needed to validate the forecast models.

OUTLOOK

Integrid will continue until the end of 2020 where Ellevio deliverables are spread throughout 2019-2020.

- The work on the fault indicators at Ekerö will

continue with the implementation of FLISR to include the whole process. The evaluation is partly dependent on that fault occur at the two distribution lines at Ekerö nevertheless, in parallel work will be performed to estimate the process steps from outage to restored power.

- At the primary substation, Kyrkviken, at Lidingö data will be collected during spring 2019 for the predictive maintenance tool that SAP are developing within Integrid.
- Data collection and in-depth studies of the data at SRS will continue during spring 2019. Moreover, work will continue with the tool for predictive maintenance.

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DISCLAIMER

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